

Project brief on implementation of Open Science and EOSC targets

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DOCUMENT AMENDMENT PROCEDURE

Amendments, comments and suggestions should be sent to the Project Manager at manager@envri-fair.eu.

GLOSSARY

The latest version of the master list of the ENVRI glossary is available in the ENVRI Community folder of ZENODO at <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4471374>.

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1 Integration with the EOSC infrastructure

Environmental Research Infrastructures (RI) in the framework of the ENVRI Science Cluster, specifically the ENVRI-FAIR project, are part of a common community with its participating RIs covering all four subdomains of the Earth system, i.e., Atmosphere, Marine, Solid Earth, Biodiversity and Ecosystems. ENVRI-FAIR encompasses 14, each with their own subdivisions and research communities, and with different maturity levels in their FAIR implementations. The heterogeneity across the RIs can be demonstrated e.g., in terms of presenting and accessing datasets - solutions in the ENVRI RIs span from machine-readable solutions (e.g., services with RESTful webAPIs) to only-human-accessible portals. Similar heterogeneity exists in semantics and data formats, from raw binary files, to CSV and proprietary formats, although in some fields well-defined standards (e.g., NetCDF) exist and are widely adopted. Semantic descriptions adopt often agreed vocabularies and standards within the RIs of one subdomain, but different vocabularies and standards are applied across the subdomains.

Similar heterogeneity exists in service and data findability. The ways of finding datasets and other digital assets, e.g., services, data products, equipment/infrastructures, vary from location-based search to parameter-based selections and/or 'keyword' terms or free-text terms. The stewarding of heterogeneous assets and resources of interest (i.e., different FAIR Digital Objects), reaches across services, datasets, to source codes or documents, workflow descriptions and scripts, training materials and more. There is variety in audiences served, spanning from individual researchers, collaborations and RIs, to automated harvesters and linked virtual research environments.

In such a complex landscape, the common goal of ENVRI RIs is to achieve interoperability through syntactic, semantic, organisational and governance harmonisation driven by technology following FAIR principles. In compliance with FAIR principles, two aspects were recognised as key to interoperability: metadata and web-service based approach:

- For the **metadata**, a rich superset metadata schema is necessary to accommodate the existing complexity of multiple heterogeneous metadata standards in use. This schema must also be able to facilitate representing information related to resources (services, datasets, codes etc.), publications, persons, organisations, facilities, equipment, authorisation details and others, in a machine-readable and machine-understandable way. Such information should be provided by communities and be part of their approach to describing datasets and other digital assets.
- For the **web-service based approach**, it was recognised that the best way to enable true machine readability and actionability is enabling any user (human or machine) to access datasets (or other digital assets) by means of web-services, that may provide full access also to functionalities associated to datasets (e.g., Findability with search functionalities and Accessibility through appropriate authentication schemas associated to policies).

The above two driving aspects are realised in the ENVRI Catalogue of Services (in EOSC terms *Profiles*), a rich metadata catalogue based on the CERIF standard that stores all details about services and other digital assets from the individual RIs to enable any user to access these seamlessly and in a machine

actionable way. The European Open Science Cloud can then be able to gain all information about RIs in the ENVRI-FAIR Science Cluster by accessing the ENVRI-FAIR Catalogue of Services metadata converted to the EOSC metadata standard(s). The ENVRI Catalogue of Services is also at the heart of the ENVRI-Hub, the ENVRI platform which will offer discovery of services and other digital assets, documented standardised interfaces, machine actionability, and re-usability as well as user support through EOSC.

Although not all details of the EOSC architecture have been defined yet, the above approach, firstly adopted in the EPOS Research Infrastructure and then scaled to other RIs within ENVRI, is the most flexible as it can accommodate different architectures and federation types by providing in all cases the information that is needed by the EOSC to interact with the nodes made available by the domain specific RIs. As the first step within ENVRI-FAIR, EPOS and LifeWatch RIs have mapped their catalogues to the evolving EOSC catalogues step-by-step so that ENVRI is ready to on-board to EOSC when the EOSC metadata standard is sufficient for access to ENVRI RIs' digital assets (both technical and governance aspects) to be managed appropriately including licensing, authorisation, citation/acknowledgement as well as metadata richness for Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability and Reuse.

2 FAIR principles implementation and repositories

The implementation of FAIR principles in the ENVRI Science Cluster builds on a structured approach: (1) assessment of the actual state of the participating RIs with respect to all aspects of FAIRness, (2) subsequent development of FAIRness implementation plans for the four subdomains of the Earth system, considering the different levels of FAIR maturity amongst the research infrastructures, and (3) continuous monitoring of progress in FAIRness implementation efforts.

To evaluate the implementation status of FAIR data practices at the level of the individual ENVRI Research Infrastructures, three assessment runs were conducted during ENVRI-FAIR so far, using a survey-based approach. During this period the approach was constantly optimized and made increasingly FAIR itself in close cooperation with GO FAIR. Whereas the human-readable questionnaire in the first run was postprocessed via YAML files into RDF, the second version was based on the FAIR Implementation Profile (FIP) ontology and implemented in DS Wizard tool (now referred to as the FIP Wizard) which captures and publishes users' responses in nanopublication format. The third run refines the FIP Wizard interface, allowing users to easily choose from answers available as nanopublication resources. This refinement also includes optimized machine-readability of the whole output.

FIPs (https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-65847-2_13) are a list of FAIR enabling resources used by the community to address each of the FAIR Guiding Principles and their implementation status. The development towards FAIRer data practices can be easily demonstrated by comparing the FIPs over time. Furthermore, FIPs can be assessed in relation to the FIPs across the ENVRI cluster in the so-called Convergence Matrix, and strategically revised to optimise and harmonise FAIR attributes of the institutional data repositories. The whole process was facilitated with domain-specific workshops and training events (introduction to the FIP approach, FIP consulting and FAIR convergence). The FAIR assessment activity helped to raise awareness and knowledge around the FAIR principles and to detect gaps in the implementation. This analysis was used by the RIs to define their individual implementation plans but also common implementation strategies that maximize FAIR convergence at subdomain level.

The common developments have been guided by both a subdomain driven approach to make use of the synergies in the respective communities, and an overarching coordination through six task forces. The task forces were set up to take care of the most important aspects of FAIRness, as identified in the analysis of the first FIP survey. The respective task forces deal with the requirements for implementation of a federated cross-RI AAAI; the definition and introduction of the ENVRI Catalogue of Services as detailed in Section 1 as centre of the ENVRI-Hub; Persistent Identification throughout the whole data lifecycle; the use of ontologies, linked open data, vocabularies, and certification of repositories; licenses, data attribution and GDPR issues; and finally, the ENVRI-Hub architecture design and demonstrations.

The intermediate reports on the progress in FAIRness implementation are accessible as “Requirement Analysis, Technology Review and Gap Analysis of ENV RIs” at <https://zenodo.org/record/3884998> and as “Implementation Plan for Common Development Goals” at <https://zenodo.org/record/4061702>. The reviews have shown that all actions in the implementation plan are mainly on schedule and updated implementation plans have now been finalised to reflect the progress made and add new improvements where needed. As the ENVRI-Hub design and architecture have now crystallised, the implementation plans could be detailed further, and work has started to fill in these details and implement the interfaces and metadata pipelines.

Main achievements include the development of tools and services that support FAIR data; actions to harmonise/standardise the FAIR principles implementation across the cluster and beyond; actions to improve institutional repositories to better support FAIR data; eventual contribution to the EOSC interoperability framework. Well-defined repositories like ZENODO are used to make products of ENVRI-FAIR and the ENVRI Community in general accessible to the public in a FAIR and open manner; visit <https://zenodo.org/communities/envri/?page=1&size=20> for an overview and access to documents. Concerning the improvement of institutional repositories, the first environmental RIs have started the process of certification of their repositories in close collaboration with FAIRsFAIR.

3 Technical, semantic, legal and organisational interoperability

In order to develop interoperable machine accessible FAIR data repositories and management services, developers from different environmental research infrastructures need agreements on the service architecture, interface, and schemas. Therefore, open standards and community recommendations on metadata, data format, and service architecture are crucial.

The investigation of open standards and common solutions started already in the previous ENVRI Community project ENVRIplus. The recommendations developed in that project include standards for metadata and cataloguing (CKAN, DCAT and CERIF), provenance (PROV, CERIF), services protocols (RESTful), and scientific workflows (CWL). Based on these standards, several tools were prototyped, e.g., provenance template, cloud infrastructure automation, data processing framework, semantic annotation, and data catalogue.

Building on this preparatory work, each ENVRI-FAIR research infrastructure evaluated the results of the FAIRness gap analysis, selected their priorities, and reviewed the best practices of the international communities as well as the recommendations for standards from different initiatives, e.g., RDA, CODATA, W3C and EOSC.

The joint task forces (see above Section 2) play a key role in gathering developers and expertise from different subdomains to discuss the requirements and compare best practices. A customised and concrete implementation plan was then set up by each research infrastructure to implement customised solutions for their infrastructure-specific data life cycle. For example, RIs and institutions experienced with terminology services (e.g., BODC in the marine domain) have extensively presented and shared their knowledge and best practices on how to set up, operate and maintain services for terminology (e.g., measured variables, sensors, etc.) with other interested RIs. As a result, additional RIs have started to re-use technologies to serve their communities with similar terminology services.

An ENVRI Community Knowledge Base is provided to support developers from different infrastructures to share development solutions, best practices, and FAIRness status. Via the search engine of the knowledge base, a user (e.g., researcher, RI manager) can discover relevant online information from the community, such as the stations operated by an RI, and get informed about the FAIRness status of the data centres operated by RIs. The Knowledge Base is another cornerstone of the ENVRI-Hub.

The role of research infrastructures is essential as they guarantee that appropriate non-technical actions are undertaken to guarantee long term sustainability of services. In the experience of ENVRI-FAIR, decoupling the technical dimension from the governance, financial and sustainability dimension would eventually impact the quality of services and their robustness. RIs are the place where these

dimensions are kept together under appropriate governance and management and further supporting actions are required to guarantee the datasets can be stewarded by RIs in a FAIR compliant, robust, and efficient way.

This “soft” dimension of service provision is being addressed in the development of the ENVRI Policy Framework, which lists the key policy decisions (-statements) needed to be made by the infrastructures to enable their sustained integration with EOSC and ENVRI-Hub service provision. This Framework is built on analysing key policy driver documents (e.g., EOSC Rules of Participation, FAIR principles, and ENVRI-Hub documentation), deriving the needed policy decisions, and joint development of the actual policy statements in common workshops.

4 Stewardship of data

ENVRI-FAIR objectives cover the further development of common standards, protocols and policies for the data life cycle, their alignment with more extensive European policies and the implementation of necessary tools for adopting an open approach for sharing data and software. A strong focus is put on the improvement of skills of research infrastructure personnel to develop and sustain knowledge on Research Data Management and FAIRness by an extensive training programme.

The FAIR training activities are among the areas producing high visibility for ENVRI-FAIR. The results and methodology of the gap analysis of FAIR training materials has been received with interest, not the least by training specialists of the other ESFRI cluster projects. Training materials are produced and made available at the training portal at <https://training.envri.eu/>, and a training catalogue has been developed in order to allow ENVRI data centres and RIs to easily search, discover and access training resources. The catalogue is today available at <https://trainingcatalogue.envri.eu/> and will become later accessible through the ENVRI-Hub.

The extensive ENVRI FAIRness training programme is based on a thorough analysis of available FAIR Training Materials. The methodology developed during the inventory and gap analysis of FAIR Training Materials is another key product of our project and will have an impact far beyond our ENVRI-FAIR since FAIR training is one of the most active areas in FAIRification. This capacity building effort targets also non-ENVRI community researchers and other end-users.

Training Activities within ENVRI-FAIR include:

- **Training course on terminologies used for environmental research infrastructures**, held on February 5, 2020 in Dresden, Germany, during the first ENVRI-FAIR week; the course provided a broad introduction into ontologies and how these can help “putting the I into FAIR”, introduced key concepts of the Semantic Web and knowledge representation techniques, and provided different examples of ontology & vocabulary portals.
- **Provenance Tracing** as high-priority training requirement for RI’s was tackled by a series of workshops in which three technical demonstrators of provenance tracing were presented and trained: (1) PROV Template approach, (2) ENVRI-FAIR demonstrator focusing on provenance and modelling a specific data production/processing workflow used at NILU, (3) EPOS Approach using the main catalogue.
- The **First International Summer School on Data FAIRness in Environmental & Earth Science Infrastructures** from 1 - 5 July 2019 in Lecce, Italy; the summer school focused on data management, and how to implement FAIR principles. The material is accessible at <https://trainingcatalogue.envri.eu/course/7>.
- The **ENVRI Community International Winter School on DATA FAIRness** on January 11-22, 2020 as virtual event which targeted staff at ENVRI data centres, researchers and PhD candidates with the aim to present state of the art technologies relevant to FAIRification of services, based on real-life use cases, encourage adoption of new technology to enhance data centre

functionality, and enable new knowledge-exchange networks for ENVRI data professionals. Material is accessible at <https://training.envri.eu/course/view.php?id=52>.

- The **2021 ENVRI Community International School on "Services for FAIRness"** on September 27 to October 8 as virtual event which extended the topics targeted in the Winter School on DATA FAIRness. Having dealt in depth with data FAIRness and data management during previous editions, the School 2021 focused on Services for FAIRness, from design to development and publication. See <https://trainingcatalogue.envri.eu/course/51> for information.
- Early 2022 (January 21 and February 27) a 2-days training event on the **unambiguous semantic representation of variables** using the RDA I-ADOPT Framework will support the semantic interoperability of RI's data.

5 Cross-cluster collaboration activities and achievements

The Science Clusters cover today environmental sciences (ENVRI-FAIR), life sciences (EOSC-Life), astronomy and particle physics (ESCAPE), photon and neutron sciences (PANOSC), and social sciences and humanities (SSHOC). They ensure strong connections between Research Infrastructures on the ESFRI Roadmap, between the Science Clusters themselves and jointly towards the EOSC. They are also seen as key for the transitioning of ESFRI RIs from servicing only their communities towards more integrated services in response to the Grand Challenges and transforming their research products for economic and societal users.

In recognition of their multiple roles in the ESFRI - EOSC landscape and to advance the related tasks, the Science Clusters have established an intense collaboration on several fields and started regular meetings of the group of ESFRI science cluster projects coordinators. Particularly, the group of Science Cluster coordinators developed into the main point of contact for the European Commission, ESFRI, EOSC Association, and ERIC forum, when it comes to topics of interest for all Science Clusters, independent of their specific research fields, expertise, and communities.

This group published cluster position papers on expectations and planned contributions to the EOSC and COVID-19 impact on research and society, developed a common view of the ESFRI clusters on the EOSC which is adopted by EOSC, and helped clarifying the role of the ESFRI Science Cluster projects in the EOSC ecosystem. Respective position papers and strategic documents are available in the ENVRI Community at ZENODO:

- ESFRI cluster projects - Position papers on expectations and planned contributions to the EOSC. The collection of position papers is published at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3675081>.
- Joint statement by the ESFRI Science Clusters on Expectations and Long-Term Commitment in Open Science. The statement is published at <https://zenodo.org/record/4892245>.
- ESFRI cluster projects position paper on COVID-19 - Why multidisciplinary environmental research matters. The position paper is published at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3734071>.

Science clusters coordinate their contributions to the EOSC Symposia to ensure as broad as possible communication of science-related requirements and contributions to EOSC and to help shaping EOSC also for the needs of the different scientific communities.

On the technical level, Science Cluster projects started to align technical developments and invite representatives of each cluster to annual meetings, thus streamlining the cluster projects workflows, and ensuring coherence of results provided by the cluster projects to EOSC.

On the communication level, the communication officers of the ESFRI cluster projects established regular meetings to coordinate communication on topics of relevance for all cluster projects and to develop communication resources which can be used by all Science Clusters.

6 Concluding remarks on the progress in the ENVRI Cluster

The Project Brief gives a clear description of the cross-RI strategic developments implemented in the ENVRI-FAIR Science Cluster project towards interoperability, and the state of interactions at Science Cluster level. Despite the good progress made and achievements gained, it must be noted that the report refers to "work-in-progress". Although FAIRness implementation will reach an encouraging level of maturity at the finalisation of ENVRI-FAIR, the achieved FAIRness at the individual RIs will be far from completion and some of the gaps ahead will still require resources allocated at RI level. This concerns not only the progressing implementation of FAIR enabling resources but also the development of interoperable science-based cross-RI services. Additionally, the further development of the ENVRI-Hub as the ENVRI collaboration platform in EOSC will require additional resources at ENVRI cluster level to make it the fully functioning EOSC portal to the ecosystem of Environmental Research Infrastructures.